

A Study of Thyroid disorder among women in First Trimester – A descriptive cross-sectional study

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ABSTRACT

Background: Among the frequent endocrine issues that pregnant women face are thyroid diseases. Due of pregnancy's hypermetabolic condition and vague symptoms, is frequently disregarded. The purpose of this study was to determine the prevalence of thyroid problems in first trimester

Aim : To assess the prevalence of thyroid disorders in first trimester

Methods: A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted among 300 first trimester antenatal mothers attending OPD in Trichy SRM Medical College, Hospital

Results: The prevalence of thyroid disorders was found to be 10.3 % out of which 9.3% was subclinical hypothyroidism and 1 % was subclinical hyperthyroidism.

Conclusions: The prevalence of thyroid disorders among first trimester mothers were on par with studies conducted in other parts of the country.

Keywords: *hypothyroidism, hyperthyroidism, antenatal, first trimester, Trichy*

INTRODUCTION

A complex metabolic stress state that involves major changes in the hormonal environment is pregnancy^{1,2}. Both the shape and function of the thyroid gland are significantly impacted.

Among the frequent endocrine issues that pregnant women face are thyroid diseases³. Even if they do conceive, women with hypothyroidism have lower fertility, a higher chance of abortion, gestational hypertension, anemia, abruption of the placenta, and postpartum haemorrhage⁴. Research has indicated that offspring born to women with hypothyroidism bear a notable higher likelihood of experiencing deficits in their cognitive capacities, neuropsychological developmental indices, and intelligence quotient (IQ)^{5,6}.

Women with subclinical thyroid illness are expected to be the majority of those identified by screening in the first trimester. 2.5% of pregnant women have hypothyroidism, and 0.1-0.4% have hyperthyroidism⁷⁻⁹.

In India various studies have been conducted among pregnant mothers to find out prevalence of thyroid disorders. This study intends to find out the prevalence of thyroid disorders in first trimester.

METHODS

Study Design & Area:

A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted among patients who came for antenatal check-up during first trimester (up to 14 weeks) at Obstetrics Gynaecology OPD in Trichy SRM Medical College, Hospital for a period of 6 months from March 2023- September 2023

Sample size:

A sample size of 300 was taken for this study. The study participants were selected by convenient sampling technique.

Inclusion criteria:

Women in First trimester during antenatal visit with singleton pregnancy

Exclusion criteria:

Multifetal gestation, people with known thyroid disorder, Diabetes, Hypertension, Heart disorder and Patients not willing for study were excluded from the study.

Study procedure:

After obtaining ethical approval from Institutional Human Ethics Committee and permission at all levels to conduct the survey, a predesigned semi-structured was used to collect relevant information. After obtaining the informed consent, all patients coming to outpatient department (OPD) in first trimester of pregnancy for regular

antenatal visits were randomly selected for the study. Following details of the patient noted: routine antenatal history taking, examination, general physical examination, height, weight, body mass index, systemic and per abdominal examination

Statistical Analysis:

Collected data was entered in Microsoft excel and statistical analysis was carried out using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) software. A Chi-square test was done to find out the prevalence of thyroid disorders in first trimester.

RESULTS

In the present study, it was found that 269 participants (89.7%) were found to be in euthyroid status, 28 participants (9.3%) were found to be in subclinical hypothyroid status and 3 participants (1%) were found to be having subclinical hyperthyroid status. (Table 1)

Table 2 shows age distribution of our study participants, the mean age was found to be 23.62 with a SD of 2.14. 17 participants were less than 20 years of age, majority (153) were between ages 21 – 25 years, 96 participants were between ages of 26 – 30 years, 27 participants were between age group of 31 – 35 years and 7 participants were in the age group between 36 – 40 years.

Table 3 shows the association between the thyroid disorders detected in the present study and its associated risk factors and pregnancy outcomes. A chi-square test was done to find statistical association between the variables and a p value of less than 0.05 was considered to be significant.

Parity was found to be statistically significant with thyroid disorders in first trimester of pregnancy. History of previous history abortion was also found to be statistically significant in case of thyroid disorders in first trimester. BMI was found to be statistically significant with thyroid disorders in first trimester of pregnancy.

DISCUSSION

The present study was undertaken in Obstetrics Gynaecology OPD in Trichy SRM Medical College Hospital among first trimester patients. This was conducted on 300 participants who were selected through convenient sampling technique. The study's primary goal was to determine the frequency of thyroid problems in pregnant women.

In our present study, the prevalence of hypothyroidism among antenatal mothers in first trimester was found to be 9.3%. Our findings are consistent with the findings of the study conducted by Rani U et al¹⁰ who studied 300 patients in first trimester and found the prevalence of subclinical hypothyroidism in our study to be 10.33%. The prevalence of hyperthyroidism in our study is 1%. This is similar to the study conducted by Sahu et al¹¹ who conducted a study on 663 patients and found a prevalence of 0.93% of hyperthyroidism in first trimester.

The most common age group checked was 21–25 years old. In contrast, Dhanwal et al¹². found that the most common age group for thyroid screening was 25.6 years, compared to 27±6 years in western countries. This finding may be explained by the early marriage and early conception that are typical in India.

Although there is disagreement on the relationship between pre-pregnancy BMI and thyroid dysfunction, our study's subclinical hyperthyroidism revealed a clear link between maternal weight and the risk of aberrant thyroid function. One risk factor is the obesity of mothers¹³.

Women who are obese are more likely to experience complications such as postoperative endometritis, prolonged surgical times, increased blood loss, and wound infections¹⁴. Many pregnant women gain too much weight, which increases their risk of complications during childbirth and increases the likelihood that they will continue to gain weight after giving birth^{15,16}.

Loss of pregnancy is a frequent clinical issue. The most common causes of pregnancy loss include a range of thyroid-related conditions; both hyperthyroidism and hypothyroidism have long been linked to an increased risk of fetal loss. Furthermore, after the underlying condition has received the proper treatment, further associations of this kind are typically reversible

LIMITATIONS

We need more studies with larger samples because the current study's sample size is so small. For a more thorough examination, we also need to monitor these individuals throughout their pregnancies and the postpartum phase.

CONCLUSION

The present study was undertaken to study thyroid disorder among pregnant women in their first trimester. Since first trimester is an important phase, this has to be viewed seriously. Antenatal mothers with thyroid disorders are at risk of pregnancy loss and other complications^{17,18}. More studies are needed for setting up some screening procedure for first trimester mothers to safeguard pregnancy¹⁹.

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Conflict of interest: there is no conflict of interest

Ethical approval: institutional human ethics committee approval was obtained

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Table 1. Distribution of cases as per diagnosis (n=300)

Diagnosis	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Normal	269	89.7
Overt hypothyroid	0	0
Subclinical hypothyroid	28	9.3
Overt hyperthyroid	0	0
Subclinical hyperthyroid	3	1
Total	300	100

Table 2. Age distribution of subjects

Age	Frequency
18 – 20 years	17
21 – 25 years	153
26 – 30 years	96
31 – 35 years	27
36 – 40 years	7

Table 3. Association between thyroid disorders and pregnancy outcomes

Variables		Normal	Hypothyroidism	Hyperthyroidism	Chi square	Df	P value
Parity	Primi	164	28	3	18.6	2	<0.05
	Multi	105	0	0			
Abortion	Nil	258	25	1	45.69	6	<0.05
	A1	7	2	1			
	A2	1	1	1			
	A3	3	0	0			
BMI	Underweight	1	0	0	9.2	2	0.01
	Normal	237	25	3			
	Overweight	13	2	0			
	Obesity	0	1	0			